

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 8

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>⁰ For the choir director; on the Gittith. A Psalm of David.</p>	
<p>¹ O LORD, our Lord, how majestic is Your name in all the earth, who have displayed Your splendor above the heavens!</p>	<p>¹ לְמִנְצַחַת עַל-הַגִּיתִית מִזְמוֹר לְדָוִד : ² יְהוָה אֲדַלְּנֵנוּ מִהַ- אֲדִיר שְׁמֶךָ בְּכָל-הָאָרֶץ אֲשֶׁר תִּנְּהָה הַיּוֹדֶךָ עַל-</p>
<p>² From the mouth of infants and nursing babes You have established strength because of Your adversaries, to make the enemy and the revengeful cease.</p>	<p>הַשָּׁמַיִם : ³ מִפִּי עוֹלָלִים וַיִּנְקִימֵם יְסֻדָּתָךְ עֵז לְמַעַן צוֹרְרֶיךָ לְהַשְׁבִּית אוֹיֵב</p>
<p>³ When I consider Your heavens, the work of Your fingers, the moon and the stars, which You have ordained;</p>	<p>וּמַתְנַקֵּם : ⁴ כִּי-אֲרָאָה שָׁמַיֶךָ מֵעֲשֵׂי אֲצַבְעֹתֶיךָ יָרַח וְכּוֹכָבִים אֲשֶׁר כּוֹנְנָתָה : ⁵</p>
<p>⁴ What is man that You take thought of him, and the son of man that You care for him?</p>	<p>מָה-אֲנוֹשׁ כִּי-תִזְכְּרֵנוּ וּבֶן- אָדָם כִּי תִבְקַדֵּנוּ : ⁶</p>
<p>⁵ Yet You have made him a little lower than God, and You crown him with glory and majesty!</p>	<p>וּתְחַסְּרֶהוּ מִעֵט מַאֲלָהִים וְכָבוֹד וְהַדָּר תַּעֲטֶהוּ : ⁷</p>
<p>⁶ You make him to rule over the works of Your hands; You have put all things under his feet,</p>	<p>תִּמְשָׁלֵהוּ בְּמַעֲשֵׂי יָדֶיךָ כָּל שִׁפְתָהּ תַחַת-רַגְלָיו : ⁸ צִנְהָה וְאֵלֶּפִים כָּלָם וְגַם בְּהֵמֹת</p>
<p>⁷ All sheep and oxen, and also the beasts of the field,</p>	<p>שָׂדֵי : ⁹ צִפּוֹר שָׁמַיִם וְדֹגֵי תַיִם עֹבֵר אֲרֻחֹת יַמִּים : ¹⁰</p>
<p>⁸ The birds of the heavens and the fish of the sea, whatever passes through the paths of the seas.</p>	<p>יְהוָה אֲדַלְּנֵנוּ מִהַ-אֲדִיר שְׁמֶךָ בְּכָל-הָאָרֶץ :</p>
<p>⁹ O LORD, our Lord, how majestic is Your name in all the earth!</p>	

Targum

Psa. 8:1 For praise, on the lyre that he brought from Gath. A hymn of David. ² O God our master, how lofty is your name and praiseworthy in all the earth, you who have placed your splendor above the heavens. ³ From the mouth of children and infants you have established strength because of your oppressors, to bring to naught the enemy and the violent man. ⁴ Because I see your heavens, the works of your fingers, the moon and the stars that you have fixed in place, ⁵ What is a son of man, because you will remember his deeds, and a son of man, because you will punish him? ⁶ And you have made him a little less than the angels, and you will crown him with glory and brightness. ⁷ You made him ruler over the works of your hands; all things you have placed under his feet. ⁸ Sheep and oxen, all of them, and also the beasts of the field. ⁹ The birds of the air, and the fish of the sea, and Leviathan, who passes along the paths of the sea. ¹⁰ O God our master, how lofty and praiseworthy is your name in all the earth!

Interlinear

Psalms 8:0 (NAS95S) For the choir director on the
 Key
 Lex
 PrtSpeech

Gittith A Psalm of David

Key H3068
 Lex יהוה
 PrtSpeech Noun

Lord	How	majestic	is	Your	name	in	all	the	earth	Who
H0136	H4100	H0117			H8034		H3605		H0776	H0834
אֲדֹנָי	מִה	אֲדִיר			שֵׁם		כָּל		אֶרֶץ	אֲשֶׁר
Noun	Pron.	Adj.			Noun		Noun		Noun	Part.

have	displayed	Your	splendor	above	the	heavens
	H5414		H1935	H5921		H8064
	נָתַן		הֹדַר	עַל		שָׁמַיִם
	Verb		Noun	Part.		Noun

Psalms 8:2 (NAS95S) From the mouth
 Key H6310
 Lex פֶּה
 PrtSpeech Noun

of	infants	and	nursing	babes	You	have	established	strength
	H5768		H3243	H3243			H3245	H5797
	עוֹלָל		יָנֵק	יָנֵק			יָסַד	עֹז
	Noun		--	--			Verb	Noun

Because	of	Your	adversaries	To	make	the
H4616			H6887c			
כִּי־עָשָׂה			יַעֲרֹב			
--			Verb			

enemy	and	the	revengeful	cease
H0340			H5358	H7673a
אֹיֵב			נָקָם	שָׁבַת
Noun			Verb	Verb

Psalms 8:3 (NAS95S)	When	I	consider
Key	H3588		H7200
Lex	כִּי		רָאָה
PrtSpeech	Part.		Verb

Your	heavens	the	work	of	Your	fingers	The	moon
	H8064		H4639			H0676		H3394
	שָׁמַיִם		מַעֲשֵׂה			אֶצְבָּע		יָרֵחַ
	Noun		Noun			Noun		Noun

and	the	stars	which	You	have	ordained
		H3556	H0834			H3559
		כּוֹכָב	אֲשֶׁר			כִּין
		Noun	Part.			Verb

Psalms 8:4 (NAS95S)	What	is	man
Key	H4100		H0582
Lex	מָה		אָנוּשׁ
PrtSpeech	Pron.		Noun

that	You	take	thought	of	him	And	the	son	of	man	that	You	ca
		H2142	H2142					H1121		H0120			H6
		זָכַר	זָכַר					בֶּן		אָדָם			קָדַשׁ
		Verb	Verb					Noun		Noun			Verb

him

Key		H2637		H4592	H2637
Lex		תָּסַר		מְעֵט	תָּסַר
PrtSpeech		Verb		Adj.	Verb

than God And You crown him with glory and majesty

H4480	H0430		H5849b		H3519b		H1926
מִן	אֱלֹהִים		עָטַר		כָּבוֹד		הִרְרָה
Part.	Noun		Verb		Noun		Noun

Psalms 8:6 (NAS95S)	You	make	him	to	rule	over	the	works
Key					H4910			H4639
Lex					מָשַׁל			מַעֲשֵׂה
PrtSpeech					Verb			Noun

of	Your	hands	You	have	put	all	things	under	his	feet
		H3027			H7896	H3605	H3605	H8478		H7272
		יָד			שִׁית	כָּל	כָּל	תַּחַת		רַגְלֵי
		Noun			Verb	Noun	Noun	Part.		Noun

Psalms 8:7 (NAS95S)	All	sheep	and	oxen	And
Key	H3605	H6792		H0504	
Lex	כָּל	צֹאֵן		אֶלֶךְ	
PrtSpeech	Noun	Noun		Noun	

also	the	beasts	of	the	field
H1571		H0929			H7706a
גַּם		בְּהֵמָה			שָׂדֵי
Part.		Noun			Noun

Psalms 8:8 (NAS95S)	The	birds	of	the	heavens	and	the	fish
Key		H6833			H8064			H1709
Lex		צִפּוֹר			שָׁמַיִם			דָּג
PrtSpeech		Noun			Noun			Noun

of	the	sea	Whatever	passes	through	the	paths	of	the	seas
		H3220		H5674a	H5674a		H0734			H3220
		יָם		עָבַר	עָבַר		אֲרָח			יָם
		Noun		Verb	Verb		Noun			Noun

Psalms 8:9 (NAS95S)
Key
Lex
PrtSpeech

O	Lord	our	Lord	How	majestic	is	Your
	H3068		H0136	H4100	H0117		
	יְהוָה		אֲדֹנָי	מָה	אֲדִיר		
	Noun		Noun	Pron.	Adj.		

name	in	all	the	earth
H8034		H3605		H0776
שֵׁם		כָּל		אֶרֶץ
Noun		Noun		Noun

Superscript

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
⁰ For the choir director; on the Gittith. A Psalm of David.	¹ לְמִנְצָחַת עַל־הַגִּתִּית מִזְמוֹר לְדָוִד :

Verse Analysis

גִּתִּית (gittit) The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament indicates that the meaning of the word is unknown and is probably a musical instrument. This word can mean "winepress." It is an allegorical expression for the grievous catastrophe which the LORD had visited upon the nations. It alludes to Israel's enemies who are destined to be crushed by the LORD like grapes in a winepress. The winepress does not wholly destroy the grape. Instead, it removes the fine and noble essence which was locked within it. This word may refer to a special kind of musical instrument.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

To the Sefirah Netzach, the Sefirah of Victory who gives triumph over one's enemies.

Verse One

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
1 O LORD, our Lord, how majestic is Your name in all the earth, who have displayed your splendor above the heavens!	יְהוָה אֱלֹהֵינוּ מִתְּאֲדִיר שְׁמֶךָ בְּכָל־הָאָרֶץ

Verse Analysis

The universal knowledge of Adonai is to be spread over the Earth. It is the power of the LORD.

עַל־הַשָּׁמַיִם (al hashamaym). This means "over the heavens." The Zohar says that the LORD is in Heaven's eighth layer when He is not on the throne in the seventh layer. The eighth layer is considered above Heaven.

יְהוָה (pronounced Adonai). The Sage Malbim called this the name of perpetual bringing forth into existence, for it is with this name that the LORD reveals himself to us utilizing all the creations which He brought out into the visible world.

שְׁמֶךָ (sheem'cha). This means "your name." The Sage Radak said that the LORD's name is Himself, and He Himself is His name.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

LORD, Your mighty Name must be told to all people of the Earth even when You are in the eighth layer of Heaven.

Verse Two

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>² From the mouth of infants and nursing babes you have established strength because of Your adversaries, to make the enemy and the revengeful cease.</p>	<p>³ מִפִּי עוֹלָלִים אֵינְקִים יִסְדֶּהָ עוֹ לְמַעַן צוֹרְרֵיךָ לְהַשְׁבִּית אוֹיֵב וּמִתְנַקֵּם :</p>

Verse Analysis

מִפִּי עוֹלָלִים (meephee ol' lym). This phrase means "from a child's mouth." Allegorically it means that if recognizing the LORD was difficult beyond human ability, it would take more than just studying His Word.

Even if humans forget the LORD's name it can never be erased from the Scripture.

The LORD's name is written in the Heavens and away from human hands but still intelligible to children. Without the knowledge of the LORD, humans would only pursue their happiness and not care for others.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

Even children will understand who the LORD is. Your foes will never banish your Name.

Verse Three & Four

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>³ When I consider Your heavens, the work of Your fingers, the moon and the stars, which You have ordained;</p> <p>⁴ What is man that You take thought of him, and the son of man that You care for him?</p>	<p>⁴ כִּי־אֲרָאָה שָׁמַיִךְ מַעֲשֵׂי אֲצַבְעֹתֶיךָ יָרַח וְכּוֹכָבִים אֲשֶׁר כּוֹנְנָתָה : ⁵ מַה־אֱנוֹשׁ כִּי־תִזְכְּרֵנּוּ וּבֶן־אָדָם כִּי תִּבְקָרֵנּוּ :</p>

Verse Analysis

Every star is a separate, unique, individual sphere in the Universe. This Psalm is uttered at the sight of the starry sky at night.

אָדָם (adam). This word means "man, mankind," and the first human's name that the LORD created. The word denotes the pure human, the representative of the LORD on Earth. His task is to realize the moral purposes for which the LORD has called the physical world into being.

An "adam" knows only his duty, seeks justification of his desires and ambition.

אֱנוֹשׁ (enosh). This word means "man, mortal man, person." When this word is used, it refers to the weaknesses, fragility, and limitations imposed upon human's nature.

David wondered why the LORD made him so frail when he was made in the LORD's image and placed him on the Earth to represent divine sovereignty.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

v. 3 – When I behold the stars in Heaven, the work of your fingers, the luminaries that you have given to each task.

v. 4 – Humans are frail, yet LORD, you remember us, and what of the children of humans that you think about us.

Verse Five

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
5 Yet You have made him a little lower than God, and You crown him with glory and majesty!	6 וְתַחֲסִיֶּהוּ מֵעַט מֵאַלְהִים וְכָבוֹד וְהִנָּהר תַּעֲטֶהוּ :

Verse Analysis

Humans are the first servants of the LORD because humans are the only creatures called upon to do their duty, morally free consciously, the only being so endowed besides the LORD, that one and absolute free force.

Despite human fragility, the LORD made humans a bit lower than the angels

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

LORD, you made us a little less than the angels, giving humans a soul to crown him/her with honor and dignity.

Verse Six

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
6 You make him to rule over the works of Your hands; You have put all things under his feet,	7 תַּמְשִׁילֶהוּ בְּמַעֲשֵׂי יְדֵיךָ כֹּל שִׁתָּה תַחַת־ רַגְלָיו :

Verse Analysis

The Sage Radak said, by virtue of his exalted soul, humans were given mastery over the entire world. Humans must not enforce his/her own pride upon others. The LORD appointed humans as His stewards in the household of this terrestrial world to fulfill His purpose. Man's purpose is to be good stewards of the Earth.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

You made humans the stewards of your creation and placed everything under them.

Verse Seven

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
7 All sheep and oxen, and also the beasts of the field,	8 צֹאֵן וְאַלְפִים כָּל־אֲנִיִּם בְּהֵמֹת שְׂדֵי :

Verse Analysis

Sheep are animals that need constant protection by humans and need humans to build shelters for them.

Cattle are animals that assume leadership in the herd by virtue of their superior strength and larger size.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

Sheep and cattle, even the beasts of the fields,

Verse Eight

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
⁸ The birds of the heavens and the fish of the sea, whatever passes through the paths of the seas.	⁹ צְפוּר שָׁמַיִם וּדְגַי תַּיִם עֹבֵר אֶרְחוֹת יַמַּיִם :

Verse Analysis

This verse is a metaphor for a movement with a specific goal.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

The birds of the sky and the fish of the sea; for he crosses over the paths of the seas.

Verse Nine

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>⁹ O LORD, our Lord, how majestic is Your name in all the earth!</p>	<p>¹⁰ יְהוָה אֱלֹהֵינוּ מִה־אֲדִיר שְׁמֶךָ בְּכָל־ הָאָרֶץ :</p>

Verse Analysis

Humans should have a life of service to the LORD.

Verse Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

LORD, your name is mighty throughout the Earth.

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

To the Sefirah Netzach, the Sefirah of Victory who gives triumph over one's enemies.

LORD, Your mighty Name must be told to all people of the Earth even when You are in the eighth layer of Heaven.

Even children will understand who the LORD is. Your foes will never banish your Name.

When I behold the stars in Heaven, the work of your fingers, the luminaries that you have given to each task.

Humans are frail, yet LORD, you remember us, and what of the children of humans that you think about us.

LORD, you made us a little less than the angels, giving humans a soul to crown him/her with honor and dignity.

You made humans the stewards of your creation and placed everything under them.

Sheep and cattle, even the beasts of the fields,

The birds of the sky and the fish of the sea; for he crosses over the paths of the seas.

LORD, your name is mighty throughout the Earth.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

